

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

Update of Deliverable 5.1 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy

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List of abbreviations used in this document

DCE: Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation

EREA: European Research Executive Agency

GA: Grant agreement

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators

NGOs: Non-governmental organisations

PMB: Project Management Board

PC: Project Coordinator

R&I: Research and Innovation

WB: Western Balkan

WBC: Western Balkan Countries

WP: Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.1 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy establishes the basis for the development of a common dissemination, communication & exploitation plan in the project. This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in GreenFORCE project, designated as “public” regarding the dissemination level. The deliverable will keep updated the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies of the project as well as identifies in detail stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and procedures agreed. This deliverable is alive and will be modified according to the project needs. The results of the strategies implemented have been revised in M18, and this document represents an updated version of the document adopted in M4. Updated version of the DCE is based on the results achieved during the 18 month implementation period of the project.

1 Project overview

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia), as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to wider policy initiatives for the WB region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; will transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and will engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, making sure that research and research management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, co-creation with academia, civil society and policy-makers at the regional level. The 5 partner organisations are: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development in Albania as the coordinating partner; University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia and Center for Economic Analyses Association (CEA) in North Macedonia, as the two regional partners; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organization based in Sweden, together with Politecnico di Torino, Italy (POLITO), as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

2 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy

An effective Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy, aims at identifying and structuring the activities leading to the communication and promotion of the project's tasks and results. This strategy outlines also the improvement of research communication for the WB partners. It defines key values of communication and sharing, target audiences, key messages, communication channels and partners' responsibilities, measurable criteria, KPIs of the outreach, and tools such as satisfaction and evaluation surveys for the open public events. The strategy fosters the quality of project communication, while also addressing confusion and/or misconceptions.

The DCE Strategy is the initial activity within Work Package (WP) 5 and presents evolving strategic strives throughout the whole project. This document will contain the strategic approach and the detailed plan for Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities. It is based on the proposed Tasks 5.1 of WP5, but

detailed further, adjusted to the timeline of the activity plan and the preliminary mapping for green transition in the Western Balkans. Additionally, document ensures effective communication and dissemination processes that help to explain the wider societal relevance of Research Excellence, strengthen the grounds for future research and innovation, and ensure uptake of results in different communities.

This dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy:

- provides guidance on the (visual) identification of the project,
- defines the dissemination objectives vis-à-vis audience's needs, in the context of project dissemination and communication deliverables and Horizon Europe Framework Programme requirements for impact and exploitation,
- identifies the stakeholders and target audiences of the project results and communications,
- presents the dissemination and communication channels and tools that were strategically chosen to fulfil the objectives,
- points to internal procedures developed within the project to optimize communication flow,
- outlines the reporting procedures, impact measures and details the implementation timeline.

This deliverable (D5.1) introduces the GreenFORCE dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy, a comprehensive and living document that outlines the tools, channels and activities to be put in place throughout the project to ensure wide acceptance and sustainability.

It is worth mentioning that as the foreseen tools are developed, this document is continuously upgraded with the newest and most relevant information.

2.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation goals and objectives

The main goal of this strategy is to present how to disseminate, communicate and exploit information in the most successful manner. All dissemination, communication and exploitation activities, tools, target groups and visibility requirements are presented here. This document is a guide throughout the whole project, and it is very important to be well defined and updated with support of all project partners.

Dissemination, communication and exploitation are fundamental activities in research projects to ensure fostering actual societal impact and the uptake of research results. The EU defines communication as "a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (1) the action and (2) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange," and dissemination as "the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium." (Haardt et al, 2019). Whereas according to H2020 Online Manual, exploitation is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking processes enabling an increase of the project impact in various societal spheres.

According to Directorate General for Research and Innovation ("How to make full use of the results of your Horizon 2020 project" EC DG for R&I Ref. Ares (2021) 2201924-30/03/2021), at the level of each project, successful dissemination activities pave the way to various additional benefits, such as

- attracting new talent,
- providing international and interdisciplinary collaboration opportunities,
- improving access to other funding prospects,
- generating new sources of income thanks to the exploitation of the results,
- contributing to societal goals,
- improving current and/or helping shape future legislation.

The objectives of this strategy are related to:

1. providing a useful set of tools and procedures for consortium partners, to help them identify and exploit communication opportunities throughout the project's lifetime;
2. establishing how the project activities, outcomes, results, and points of learning, can and will be disseminated and promoted to wider public (different tools for different target audiences);
3. successfully reaching the project's target groups.

The specific objectives of Work package WP5 – Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability are:

1. To publicly disseminate the activities and results of the project through a project website and social media.
2. To promote the project and partners, enhance its visibility, domestically and internationally.
3. To share the knowledge on green transition in WB with the societal actors.
4. To ensure sustainability of project results and innovative collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

According to the Grant Agreement and the internal project management rules, most of dissemination, communication and exploitation-oriented activities are done within a separate Work Package devoted to dissemination and communication activities (WP5), where, under the coordination of Co-PLAN as a Lead Beneficiary, all partners actively contribute to planning and production of informational materials by (1) an early announcement of events, (2) providing informative reporting texts on results (e.g., articles, blogposts, news pieces, publications), (3) sending the relevant information on outputs and results to the WP5 Leader, and (4) promoting GreenFORCE events and other activities also on their local websites and information channels. Partners (WP Leaders, organizers of events) also support the WP5 team by providing sufficient visuals to accompany communication materials (e.g., photos of events, flyers, posters, pictures to accompany calls and announcements of events). Producers of these materials are responsible to align those visuals with the general GreenFORCE style guide through the use of templates and internal instructions.

2.2 General outline of the DCE strategy

When preparing this document, we took the main differences between dissemination, communication, and exploitation into account.

Dissemination focuses only on the results and their promotion towards stakeholders/potential users while communication means promotion towards multiple audience from the beginning of the project and includes both, general project information, and project results. The exploitation part directly presents the use of project results, which need to be shared as soon as ready, for commercial purposes or public policymaking. Regarding dissemination communication and exploitation, we recall the table with indicators in the Description of the Action (part B), Chapter 2.2 and Chapter 2.3 - Measures to maximize the impact, see below.

Table 1. DCE instruments, target groups and measurable targets

DCE medium and means	General target groups	Measurable targets (and WP involved)
Project branding (logo and templates)	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	Project logo design, and overall brand identity i.e.: colour palette, formatting (leaflet, brochure, rollup banner, press releases, , e-newsletter, etc.); project roll-up banner (5 in total/1 per country); 1000 brochures with infographics; 400 leaflets reaching at least 1000 recipients. (WP5)
Project website, referred as a primary source by social media	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	2000 page views per year, 6000 in total. (WP5)
Social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and Researchgate)	Policy makers; Stakeholders; Academic sector	Over 700 followers; at least 1 post per week on social media networks (FB , twitter, LinkedIn or IG) .(WP5)
E-newsletter (connected to weblog) informing experts on project deliverables/results useful for other practitioners	Policy makers; Stakeholders	1000 recipients; Published 2 times per year; 6 times in 3 years. (WP5)
Media-releases: articles in newspapers, magazines, impact on radio or TV	General public	Drafting press releases for national TVs and other web-portals, at least twice a year by each WB partner. (WP5)
Scientific conferences	Academic sector and practitioners	2 international scientific conferences in the WB organised by the WB partner universities, at least 200 recipients; one final event at least 50 recipients; one workshop on "green transition in the WB" at the EWRC; contribution to or co-organisation of regional events with RCC, NALAS and TG-WeB. (WP2,WP4, WP5)
Annual meeting	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	At least one annual meeting of TG-WeB. (WP4, WP5)
Policy briefs/reports	Project partners; Policy makers	5 policy briefs published in journals (WP2, WP5)
Open lectures	Project partners; Academic sector	1 per University/per teaching event 3 in total. (WP3, WP5)
Large dissemination events	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers;	3 large dissemination events (up to 250 participants). (WP5)

	Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	
Final dissemination event	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	At least 50 participants. (WP5)
Open-access publications in Scientific journals	Academic sector; Policy makers; Stakeholders	Drafting and submitting for publication 3 joint scientific papers based on the research of WP4, and at least 1 paper per WB organisation, focusing on own country (WP3,WP5)
Open-access book	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	Drafting the content for 1 edited open-access book (WP3)

Possible reinforcements between dissemination, communication and exploitation are not excluded. Therefore, some of the tools that will be used, and presented further in the text, are useful for all of them. The Consortium implements a periodic review of this document (in M18) to ensure it includes up-to-date contents and opportunities for disseminating and communicating the project information. In addition, as strategies are evaluated, updates are made as needed.

2.3 DCE workflows with partners

In order to have a successful internal communication and full commitment from all partner organisations, a table with contact person details – regarding the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation– has been created (see Annex 2).

Each WP leader will have a responsibility to provide key elements from the respective work package that will be posted on project website and social media channels. Also, GreenFORCE website is designed to provide relevant information - not only the project's activities, but also other relevant for areas covered in the project - which requires contribution from all project partners.

2.4 Visibility requirements

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets/factsheets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate)¹:

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

¹ According to the Article 17.2 of the GA

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Each of the tools created, materials and publicity measures must and will include:

- EU emblem (EU flag) - to download a high-resolution emblem and to find more information please visit https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter
- presence of the statement "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."
- GreenFORCE project logo – available as part of the branding package.

2.5 Languages

The official language of the project is English. Therefore, both internal and external communication, as well as dissemination, communication and exploitation activities, are performed in English language. However, as one of the key activities of the project is to reach all stakeholders from WB countries, but also throughout Europe, for some specific messages local language might be necessary. Therefore, we will use the following approach throughout the whole project:

- All main information provided on the project website and social media channels are in English.
- Sharing of the main information through partners' DCE channels could and should be translated in each partner's local language.
- Partners are encouraged to choose wisely what information to translate and share.
- When some information is highly relevant for all regions, project partners will be timely informed to translate on their local language and share it (Co-PLAN will sent this information and emphasize its importance to the partners).

3 Target groups

The identification of target groups of GreenFORCE project is crucial in order to customise the messages and dissemination & communication activities to every different group. Each target group have different points of interest and demands regarding the project. According to this strategy, messages must be shaped and delivered in an effective manner. Identification of target groups provides a clear focus of the core audience, since it is impossible to reach everyone at once. Dissemination tools should be created according to the needs of these groups, for dissemination to be successful.

As it was mentioned before, key stakeholders are representatives from educational and research institutions, governance, business sector and citizenship. Moreover, wider public is expected to be informed about the realization of project activities.

The target groups that benefit from the project results are described in circles (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The target groups of GreenFORCE

Four main groups of stakeholders or target audiences for the GreenFORCE communication, dissemination and exploitation activities have been identified:

- Core group of 29 researchers from the consortium – 17 researchers from the WB participating organizations and 12 researchers of the EU partner organisations,
- Constellation of researchers connected to, but not responsible for GreenFORCE - researchers beyond those directly responsible for the implementation of the project, but still directly interacting with the project. This is a mixed group and includes: researchers in all of the involved institutions that will have first access to the knowledge produced within their institutions,
- Societal actors directly benefiting from dissemination, exploitation and networking - this third circle is composed by two categories: a) approximately students and scientists, mostly from the WB, who will benefit from the new knowledge on green transition in the WB through the dissemination and exploitation activities, such as international conferences; b) policy makers and other societal actors related to green transition, such as civil society organisations and industries,
- The fourth and final beneficiary target group is the society at large.

4 Communication tools

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are spread throughout the whole project.

State-of-play September 2022:

The first communication action developed after the starting of the project was to create a recognizable brand of GreenFORCE reflecting the main goals of the project and offering to the audience/stakeholders a clear

identification of the values and messages. At the very beginning the wider public should be informed about the project - its goals, foreseen activities and impact. Partners' dissemination channels are used for announcement of the project.

Simultaneously, social media accounts are created, and a team of web-developers is working on the project website. With contributions from all project partners, the development of the project website was set as a priority and will be launched not later than M4 of the project.

In order to create a full project identity, a project promotional package is developed till the end of the 3rd project month. This package includes project logo and brand guide (power point template, word template, newsletter template, email address, etc.), leaflets, roll-up banner and e-newsletter. This package designed and agreed by all project partners is already included as one of the annexes of this document. The branding and promotional package is also available to all project partners in Trello platform.

Press releases, as well as partners' communication tools (partners' websites, social media accounts, local/regional newspapers, etc.) will be used for providing significant support for wider dissemination, easier communication and higher engagement.

4.1 Project logo

A foundation of the project identity is the project logo. Therefore, the initial activities of the project promotional package included designing a couple of project logos and choosing the most appropriate one by collecting votes from all partners. The first 2 Elements represent the Twinning Process of the Project. As they merge, they create a new colour and a new shape, which symbolises the shared experience. The lines overlapping represent the different perspectives and experiences as they interact and transition into each other. The chosen slogan "Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans" clearly represents the aim of the project and creates a vision for our story. The logo is made of 2 different fonts. For the word "Green", Acumin Variable Medium is used. Acumin is a very balanced font. In this case the Medium version is used to express exactly that balance that nature has and which is needed to achieve Green Transition. For the word "FORCE" the font Bebas Neue is used. This font has a bold identity, which makes it suitable to represent something strong and powerful as the word Force. To make it even more evident the Bold version is used for the logo.

The project logo is used in all project documents and announcements. The GreenFORCE Logo must always be positioned at the top left of every project's product, document, or digital media produced. Except for social media banners when for design and visibility reasons it can be placed in the centre.

The logo should NEVER be changed and/or stretched, its colours, font, and the ratio between text and icon should always remain the same. In the case of multi-coloured background, a white stripe CAN be added under the logo to ensure full visibility. In case of a dark background, the secondary white text version of the logo can be used.

Figure 2. GreenFORCE logo

4.1.1 Logo Size

Templates have been prepared for possible products that will be generated for the project. Those templates must be followed by all partners.

In order to create new products, the rules below should be followed.

- The project logo must be at least 1.3 cm in height, subsequently, its width will be 3.2171 cm, in A4 documents and other documents of similar size.
- For bigger documents and/or materials the size should change depending on the size of the specific product, making sure all visibility rules mentioned above are followed.

Colour codes of the project logo could be found in the following table:

Table 2. Colour codes of the project logo

Main Colour Palette	Yellow Orange: #FAA737
	Eton Blue: #7BC9AA
	Moss Green: #908D45
	Granite Grey: #606161
Complementary Colour Palette	Orange: #FD8000
	Apricot: #FFCEBA
	2nd Green: #3B746F

Products generated for the project must follow this colour palette when creating documents, charts, etc., and/or visibility materials.

4.2 Fonts

The project will have 2 official fonts, both come by default on every Windows Office suite.

Corbel: Corbel and all its variations will be used as the primary font for all documents generated for the project. Such products include Official letters, agendas, invitations, reports, etc. This font will be used mainly for body text.

Trebuchet MS: Trebuchet MS is the secondary font. This font may be used mostly for bigger products that need bold headlines, such as roll-up banners, publication covers, PowerPoint presentations, posters, etc. This font can NOT be used for body text in documents, reports, letters, etc.

Table 3. Main Font Size on documents

Type of Text	Font	Size	Details
Titles	Corbel Bold	16	Main Titles, <i>All Caps Optional</i>
Subtitles	Corbel Bold	11	Secondary Titles such as Subchapters, <i>All Caps Optional</i>
Body Text	Corbel Regular	10	Body Text
	Corbel Italics	10	Body Text
	Corbel Bold	10	Body Text

4.3 E-mail Signature

When communicating about GreenFORCE project, all partners should use the project-specific signature in their mail correspondence, as below:

Name Surname

Position

NGO/ Institution

City, Country

web: <https://greenforcetwinning.net/>

The Signatures font, colour, logo, size, and information should NOT be changed/ modified. The only exception is if it is necessary to add the contact number of the person sending the e-mail. In this case, the number should be added right under the website, with the same font and size.

4.4 Project website

The project website is referred as a main media hub of the project and primary source by social media. The website will inform on: the project partners and activities (all WPs); resources and methodologies; policy and societal communication. The site will link to the twinning partners websites for local access and more resources on green transition, and to science repositories. The Project Coordinator (PC) will create and maintain the website, but all partners will contribute with input proportionally to their engagement; CEA will assist PC in running the

website and social media on content level. Each partner will have an assigned account to access the website and be able to prepare posts and publish them. The account rights will be restricted to rights sufficient to produce posts, publish posts, and primarily content managing rights. Partners will not be able to edit design of the agreed website structure/ or access any features that relate to the overall functioning of the website. PC vouches for the sustainability of the website and its content, after the duration of the project.

From October 31, 2022, the project website is accessible at the following address: <https://greenforcetwinning.net/>

4.5 Social media

In addition to the project website, we use social media for distributing information related to our project and for engaging both target groups and the wider public. Social media enables rapid dissemination of news related to the project and green transition in general.

Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube and ResearchGate accounts are used to communicate/disseminate project related information/news, and we aim to share at least one post per week. These networks will be mainly run by Co-PLAN with the assistance of CEA and with contents for postings from all partners.

In order to reach the target post number, responsible people for DCE from each organisation feed the website (consequently providing content for social media) according to a rotating schedule, resulting approximately in a post every 5th week for each partner, officially starting from 1st November 2022. This approach will involve all partners to jointly achieve increased public awareness and interest in green transition. As news, announcements and relevant events could not be scheduled in the defined week, there is a possibility for switches, changes and updates of the schedule.

Web statistics related to each of these tools, as number of clicks and engagements (views, likes, comments, responses, shares) are used for monitoring and evaluation purposes.

In addition to the project's social media accounts, we will also use the accounts of beneficiary organisations for sharing and reposting, in order to reach a wider audience. This step is especially necessary at the beginning of the project. Furthermore, all partners should use their own social media accounts to attract more followers to the project's accounts.

Regarding the social media, we apply the Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf), provided by the European Commission, which includes suggestions and directions how to use social media in Horizon 2020 projects.

X platform, formerly known as Twitter People use X platform, formerly known as Twitter to find out what is going on in the world right now, instantly sharing information and connecting with people and businesses across the globe. It offers a great opportunity for GreenFORCE to reach an international audience of current and potential stakeholders. X allows text of up to 280 characters, which excludes media attachments (photos, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets, but includes links (URL is always altered to 23 characters).

Being short and concise is the core of X's existence. Every Tweet should be focused only on one message. We will post short comments and relevant announcements, as well as retweeting relevant content.

We will try to transform each project activity to short, but strong messages.

GreenFORCE X account: @greenforcetp

Figure 3. GreenFORCE X account

4.5.1 Facebook

Facebook posts do not have character limits and they can and should be enriched with photos, GIFS, videos, links, etc.. We will use a Facebook page to allow each contact person for WP5, from each organization, to share content and to have a page overview. Facebook page will be used for sharing basic project information, topic related news, as well as announcement of events.

GreenFORCE Facebook page: Greenforce Twinning Project

Figure 4. GreenFORCE Facebook page

4.5.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is currently a main business network used globally. Many of the stakeholders, which GreenFORCE needs to connect with, are in LinkedIn, so it is appropriate to implement some actions.

A LinkedIn company page will establish GreenFORCE public image on a global scale as a reputable and trustworthy project. Although many people view the Social Media site LinkedIn only as a site for job hunters and for growing professional network, LinkedIn is an equally effective tool for nurturing referral relationships. LinkedIn posts also have no character limits, photos, links, GIFs, etc.

As LinkedIn is a networking site for professionals, we believe to reach many stakeholders and policy makers.

GreenFORCE LinkedIn page: [https://www.linkedin.com/in/greenforce-twinning-project /](https://www.linkedin.com/in/greenforce-twinning-project/)

4.5.3 Instagram

Instagram is a free photo and video sharing app available on iPhone and Android. People can upload photos or videos to our service and share them with their followers or with a select group of friends. They can also view, comment and like posts shared by their friends on Instagram.

We will use an Instagram to upload photographs and short videos, follow other stakeholders feeds, and geotag images with the name of a location. We will also connect GreenFORCE Instagram account to other social networking sites, enabling them to share uploaded photos to those sites.

We will use Instagram hashtags to help users discover both photos and each other and encourages users to make tags both specific and relevant.

GreenFORCE Instagram account: Greenforce_twinning_project

Figure 5. GreenFORCE Instagram account

4.5.4 YouTube

YouTube is an online video sharing and social media platform and is the second most visited website, after Google Search. YouTube has more than 2.5 billion monthly users who collectively watch more than one billion hours of videos each day. All YouTube users can upload videos up to 15 minutes each in duration. Users can verify their account, normally through a mobile phone, to gain the ability to upload videos up to 12 hours in length, as well as produce live streams. Videos can be at most 256 GB in size or 12 hours, whichever is less. Automatic closed captions using speech recognition technology when a video is uploaded is available in 13 languages and can be machine-translated during playback.

We will use YouTube to upload the video materials from various types of the events as well as for the live streaming if it is necessary.

GreenFORCE YouTube channel: Greenforce Twinning Project

4.6 The importance of hashtags

Hashtags enable expansion of the reach. The hashtag creates searchable keywords or phrases, that help those who took part in a particular activity to search for related posts using the activity's hashtag.

Main hashtags are: #GreenFORCEtwinning #GreenFORCE #changesforgreen #greencommunity #WBC #WBCgreenFORCE #WesternBalkans #Innovation #Research #Collaboration #Twinning #HorizonEU Additional hashtags regarding an event or sharing content will be further defined.

4.7 E-newsletter

A biannual newsletter will be issued to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly updated on the project's developments. It will be circulated via the project's mailing list but also via all partners' media platforms as links. Each project partner will contribute to the content of the newsletter as it feeds its content mainly from the website posts. As it is one of the key sub-tasks within the DCE activities, each partner will be asked if there are additional news to be reported before the newsletter will be circulated. CEA will lead and coordinate the content creation.

In particular, each WP leader should have a clear overview of the activities performed within it. In that way, it will be easier to create the content of the e-newsletter that requires a clear and concise summary of project activities.

Each WP leader will be required to send a short summary of the performed activities in the previous period, as well as ideas and suggestions for the content of the newsletter, on the first working day of the defined month for the release of the e-newsletter.

CEA will structure the e-newsletter content as per agreed timeline and distribute to all project partners to review and finalize it together.

4.8 Press releases/Appearances in the media

Press releases to local newspapers, regional or national TVs, radio stations, and web portals, help to expand project information and results of the activities at national and regional level. The biggest advantage is that they reach high audience. At least twice a year by each WB partner releases are defined during the whole project implementation. In general, we will distribute at least one media release per half-year with the most important news, project activities and results (already provided for the e-newsletter).

4.9 Other materials

Printed materials – leaflets/factsheets, roll-up banner as well as project templates – PPT template, word template, newsletter template as a part of the branding guide are delivered and available on Trello platform for all beneficiaries.

4.10 Internal communication

Successful internal communication leads to a successful project dissemination. Support and dedication are needed from each partner, for every activity to be properly disseminated without missing out relevant information. Trello platform is used for overall project management including WP5 management, with additional support of e-mail communication between partners when necessary. As common understanding is extremely important at any phase of the project, platforms such as Zoom are used for even better communication. This approach facilitates the overall coordination and decision-making processes.

To ensure efficient and effective communication, numerous templates have been produced and included as part of this strategy, regulating communication of:

- Events (both in person/online)
- Social media posts
- Website maintenance + Updating, etc.

4.11 Trello platform

Trello platform is used for effective overall project management, coordination of the work between project participants, document management and communication between partners.

Communication within the consortium takes place mostly online, through e-meetings, e-mails and the Trello platform. The arrangements for the communication are provided in the Consortium Agreement. Besides those arrangements, each final deliverable and task and sub-task final output will be uploaded in Trello. The latter include papers that are not deliverables, presentations, workshop/meeting/events agendas, minutes of meetings/events, photos of events, etc. The use of Trello is necessary for guaranteeing the timely archiving of any kind of outputs related to the implementation of the project at any level, from sub-tasks to deliverables.

Within the overall project management, every WP has its own Trello card which offers multiple functions. WP5 Trello card is used to manage tasks foreseen within the respective WP, collect the necessary input and share the relevant information and documents with all the project partners. A specific card with information and templates for branding was created in Trello so that every partner could easily find dissemination templates and materials. Time management is also visible on Trello, which is one of the key elements in project coordination. After any change made on platform, as well as deadlines and scheduled meetings, all the partners registered to that activity (card) are informed instantly via their registered e-mails and allowed to participate in discussions and other actions related to the project activity.

Figure 6. GreenFORCE board on Trello platform

4.12 Internal meetings

Regarding the overall project management and coordination led by Co-PLAN, WP1 foresees one kick-off meeting and 36 Project Management Board (PMB) meetings (5 of them in person). The kick-off meeting was held online on 4th July 2022, at the very beginning of the project. It is expected for PMB meetings to be scheduled every month and to gather project partners face-to-face for five in-person meetings distributed in time and place as shown in the Calendar of Events. If any problems are experienced, considering the current global situation, the PMB meetings will be organized by using video conferences, as their aim is to present and discuss the progress of project activities, present the achieved results and agree on the action plan for the following period.

5 Dissemination and exploitation activities

Different activities are foreseen to disseminate project results. All activities will be documented in an appropriate table, supported with additional documents as evidence.

The organizers of each event should provide a full information package to the participants including draft agenda, letter of invitation and a note on the logistics. Each event should be documented by some, or all, when appropriate, of the given materials: news/event review, agenda, list of participants/trainees, report, gallery, presentations (upon the approval of the presenter), video materials (upon approval of participants).

5.1 Local meetings for mapping and engagement

These meetings are directly linked to WP4 and are expected to support the participatory mapping, engaging local stakeholders and communities to reveal local knowledge in each WB territory. This kind of meetings could

provide two-way communication, through which information about the project will be disseminated, but also information for realization of its activities will be collected.

5.2 Open-access scientific publications in high-rated journals

It is expected that GreenFORCE project develops a significant amount of research results which will be disseminated to different key scientific communities. Thus, scientists from academia will dedicate strong efforts in publishing scientific papers under the framework of global recognized scientific conferences and journals that count on high impact index.

The publications will be made freely and openly available via online repository like ZENODO, one of the repository approved by the EC, GERY repository from UB-GEF etc.

Open-access publications are especially emphasized in the overall project idea. Academics, policy makers and all stakeholders could access them without any financial, legal or technical barriers, and in that way to use project research and results.

The GreenFORCE website <https://greenforcetwinning.net/> will include articles summarizing the scientific publications in a divulgative way and will be submitted to CORDIS Wire.

5.3 Policy briefs

Policy briefs and recommendations are part of WP2, which is led by Nordregio, targeting mainly policy-makers and practitioners for different target groups to receive adequate and tailored messages. Nordregio is responsible for developing Policy briefs are short documents (2-8 pages) presenting research results in more approachable language and picking a few policy-relevant messages, possibly including a list of policy recommendations and engagement strategies for the tailored recommendations, which Policy Briefs are disseminated in cooperation with other project partners, to selected groups of recipients in each WB territory. These policy briefs will help policy makers to adopt the use the outputs of GreenFORCE to enable practitioners make informed decisions.

5.4 Participation in external events, scientific congresses and conferences

The events, international conferences, congresses, workshops, exhibitions and fairs are one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow to connect with stakeholders and the general public, encourage networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also feed of content the communication channels and tools (website, Social Media, press releases) generating great impacts on different audiences.

Each partner is encouraged to attend as many external events related to Green Transition and/or its dimensions as far as possible and at least once during the project duration. It is important to keep the presence of the project in Science, Research and Innovation events that are organized in the WBCs, even after the completion of the project.

5.5 Dissemination and exploitation through partners' dissemination tools and networking resources

In addition to the dissemination tools of each partner's organisation, GreenFORCE has also well-established dissemination networks through each partner. WP5 leader will take into consideration all tools and established relations in the process of dissemination and exploitation. Also, each partner is encouraged to suggest ideas and best practices for dissemination and exploitation in accordance with its own networks.

Policy briefs (T2,4), and the work carried in Task2.3, including a joint proposal for regional partnership will facilitate exploitation of the project results in tasks 5.4 and 5.6. This task aims at strengthening partners' capacities in using quality research in pushing forward policy agendas. The joint proposal will more specifically be the basis for interaction with NALAS, the Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe (<http://www.nalas.eu>), and RCC, the Regional Cooperation Council (<https://www.rcc.int/home>), to discuss ways to enable macroregional partnerships. The networks have provided letters of support and engagement for GreenFORCE, as networks where green transition is high on the respective agendas and representing a large number of regional stakeholders and interests.

6 Monitoring and Evaluation

The progress reports which are part of WP1, as well as the impact measurement and evaluation activities which are also part of WP1, foresee monitoring of all Key Performance Indicators, including the key indicators on communication, dissemination, public engagement and awareness-raising. These activities monitor the progress made against the indicators set in this strategy. These indicators serve as goals which must be fulfilled and later, as guides for monitoring the activities related to Dissemination & Communication.

The initially defined main indicators regarding the Dissemination & Communication are:

- design of high-quality, recognizable and appealing project logo
- branded templates for project memorandum, power point presentation, reports and media posts
- 1 project roll-up banner per country (5 in total)
- 400 project leaflets/factsheets per country/in total
- 2000 website views per year (6000 in total)
- over 400 followers on social networks
- at least one post per week on social network (52 posts per year on social networks)
- distributed e-newsletter 2 times per year (6 in total) aiming an audience of 1000 recipients
- at least 3 local meetings per WB territory (6 in total)
- 3 open dissemination events including live streaming up to 250 participants
- 50 stakeholders participating in 4 workshops for co-design
- drafting and submitting for publication 6 joint scientific papers
- one open-access book
- 2-3 external participation GreenFORCE will be communicated

7 Green-FORCE Dissemination reporting

Keeping record of all dissemination and exploitation activities is particularly important part of this strategic document.

The table for recording all dissemination and exploitation activities is presented in Annex 6.1 and 6.2. It is available on Trello platform for each partner to be able to update it when necessary. The table is adjusted to the requirements from EC in the online portal.

This table is prepared with input from all project beneficiaries and presents a database of all dissemination and exploitation activities implemented. For any additional needs and requirements, additional documents might be created.

7.1 Guidance for reporting on dissemination events and activities

Partners of the consortium will attend relevant events, conferences, workshops and fairs of the sector. They should be actively involved seeking opportunities to present and showcase the project in their own countries and at both local and European levels. The participation in events must be previously communicated to CEA and Co-PLAN (in order to make visible activities through communication channels), and after the event every partner must complete the reporting events template with the reporting about the dissemination activity: sum-up, number of attendees, pictures, publications, presentations, press clipping, etc.

Each dissemination event or activity noted in the table must be supported by additional pdf documents for appropriate evidence. For that purpose, we use the following templates:

- Annex 1: Branding Package of GreenFORCE project
- Annex 2: Contact persons form each beneficiary organisation related to implementation of DCE strategy
- Annex 3: Overall project calendar of events and activities to be implemented and reported in the framework of the DCE strategy for the website
- Annex 4: Schedule on the project beneficiaries responsibility to provide information and input for project website and social media
- Annex 5: Template for monthly collecting information/reporting about DCE activities and events for GreenFORCE
- Annex 6: Table for reporting on dissemination activities
- Annex 7: Event Report Template
- Annex 8: Agenda template
- Annex 9: List of participants template
- Annex 10: Social Media Activity Template.

8 Annexes

Annex 1: Branding Package of GreenFORCE project [is a separate file attached to the strategy]

Annex 2: Contact persons form each beneficiary organisation related to implementation of DCE strategy

Annex 3: Overall project calendar of events and activities to be implemented and reported in the framework of the DCE strategy for the website

Annex 4: Schedule on the project beneficiaries responsibility to provide information and input for project website and social media

Annex 5: Template for monthly collecting information/reporting about DCE activities and events for GreenFORCE

Annex 6: Table for reporting on dissemination activities

Annex 7: Event Report Template

Annex 8: Agenda template

Annex 9: List of participants template

Annex 10: Social Media Activity Template

Annex 2: Contact persons form each beneficiary organisation related to implementation of DCE strategy

Name	Surname	Position	Institution	Phone	E-mail
Enkela	Poro	Junior Researcher	Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development	+355 692882843	enkela_poro@co-plan.org
Igor	Mitevski	Researcher	Center for Economic Analyses	+38977656334	igor_sci@yahoo.com
Elena	Todella	Research Assistant	Politecnico di Torino	+393394117190	elena.todella@polito.it
Milan	Radovic	PhD Candidate	University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography	+381656540200	milan.radovic@gef.bg.ac.rs
Annika	Östman	Senior Communications Advisor	Nordregio	+46707205819	annika.ostman@nordregio.org

Annex 3: Overall Calendar of Events

Calendar of Events												
2022												
June 0	July 1	Aug 2	Sep 3	Oct 4	Nov 5	Dec 6						
	Kick-off			PMB meeting Tirane								
				CoDesign Wsh WP4 (2) Online								
					Online WSH on Scientific Pub. Plan							
2023												
Jan 7	Feb 8	Mar 9	Apr 18	May 11	Jun 12	Jul 13	Aug 14	Sep 15	Oct 16	Nov 17	Dec 18	
			PMB meetings Tirane		PMB meetings Belgrade			PMB meeting Turin (linked to Summer School)		Online Wsh on Proposals Writing		
	ThWsh 1 Research Agenda Online		Online Wsh on Proposals Writing		Annual Conference UB-GEF (22 June)	Online_Policy Writing				ThWsh 2 Research Agenda		
19 - 20 January 2023 WSH in Skopje Scientific Pub. Plan			Secondments CoPLAN policy influencing		Secondments Nordregio Conference					Secondments Nordregio Thematic B2B wsh		
			Teaching CEA & UB-GEF to U_Polis	Teaching POLITO to U_Polis						Teaching UB-GEF to POLITO		
								18-23 Sept. Summer School POLITO				
2024												
Jan 19	Feb 28	Mar 21	Apr 22	May 23	Jun 24	Jul 25	Aug 26	Sep 27	Oct 28	Nov 29	Dec 30	
					RAB 2 Tirana							
				PMB meetings Belgrade/Stockholm					EWRC Workshop			
		ThWsh 3 Research Agenda Online			ThWsh 4 Research Agenda			TAW Conference POLIS			ThWsh 4 Research Agenda Online	
	Co-assessment Wsh WP4 (2) Online			Secondments Nordregio Conference				Secondments CEA policy influencing				
			Teaching CEA & U_Polis to UB-GEF	Teaching POLITO to UB-GEF						Teaching CoPLAN/POLIS to POLITO		
				Summer School UB-GEF								
2025												
Jan 31	Feb 32	Mar 33	Apr 34	May 35	Jun 36							
				RAB 3 Tirane								
			PMB meetings Tirane									
	RCC Regional Event Sarajevo			Final Project Event WB								
			NALAS General Assembly meet.									
			Summer School U_POLIS									

Legend

- Teaching Exchange
- Summer School
- Secondments
- PMB in person meetings
- Conferences/workshops
- RAB meetings in person

Annex 4: Schedule on the project beneficiaries responsibility to provide information and input for project website and social media

	Co-PLAN	CEA	POLITO	UB-GEF	NORDREGIO
01.11.2022	X				
07.11.2022		X			
14.11.2022			X		
21.11.2022				X	
28.11.2022					X
05.12.2022	X				
12.12.2022		X			
19.12.2022			X		
26.12.2022				X	
02.01.2023					X
09.01.2023	X				
16.01.2023		X			
23.01.2023			X		
30.01.2023				X	
06.02.2023					X
13.02.2023	X				
20.02.2023		X			
27.02.2023			X		
06.03.2023				X	
13.03.2023					X
20.03.2023	X				
27.03.2023		X			
03.04.2023			X		
10.04.2023				X	
17.04.2023					X
24.04.2023	X				
01.05.2023		X			
08.05.2023			X		
15.05.2023				X	
22.05.2023					X
29.05.2023	X				
05.06.2023		X			
12.06.2023			X		
19.06.2023				X	

	Co-PLAN	CEA	POLITO	UB-GEF	NORDREGIO
26.06.2023					X
03.07.2023	X				
10.07.2023		X			
17.07.2023			X		
24.07.2023				X	
31.07.2023					X
07.08.2023	X				
14.08.2023		X			
21.08.2023			X		
28.08.2023				X	
04.09.2023					X
11.09.2023	X				
18.09.2023		X			
25.09.2023			X		
02.10.2023				X	
09.10.2023					X
16.10.2023	X				
23.10.2023		X			
30.10.2023			X		
06.11.2023				X	
13.11.2023					X
20.11.2023	X				
27.11.2023		X			
04.12.2023			X		
11.12.2023				X	
18.12.2023					X
25.12.2023	X				
01.01.2024		X			
08.01.2024			X		
15.01.2024				X	
22.01.2024					X
29.01.2024	X				
05.02.2024		X			
12.02.2024			X		
19.02.2024				X	
26.02.2024					X

	Co-PLAN	CEA	POLITO	UB-GEF	NORDREGIO
04.03.2024	X				
11.03.2024		X			
18.03.2024			X		
25.03.2024				X	
01.04.2024					X
08.04.2024	X				
15.04.2024		X			
22.04.2024			X		
29.04.2024				X	
06.05.2024					X
13.05.2024	X				
20.05.2024		X			
27.05.2024			X		
03.06.2024				X	
10.06.2024					X
17.06.2024	X				
24.06.2024		X			
01.07.2024			X		
08.07.2024				X	
15.07.2024					X
22.07.2024	X				
29.07.2024		X			
05.08.2024			X		
12.08.2024				X	
19.08.2024					X
26.08.2024	X				
02.09.2024		X			
09.09.2024			X		
16.09.2024				X	
23.09.2024					X
30.09.2024	X				
07.10.2024		X			
14.10.2024			X		
21.10.2024				X	
28.10.2024					X
04.11.2024	X				

	Co-PLAN	CEA	POLITO	UB-GEF	NORDREGIO
11.11.2024		X			
18.11.2024			X		
25.11.2024				X	
02.12.2024					X
09.12.2024	X				
16.12.2024		X			
23.12.2024			X		
30.12.2024				X	
06.01.2025					X
13.01.2025	X				
20.01.2025		X			
27.01.2025			X		
03.02.2025				X	
10.02.2025					X
17.02.2025	X				
24.02.2025		X			
03.03.2025			X		
10.03.2025				X	
17.03.2025					X
24.03.2025	X				
31.03.2025		X			
07.04.2025			X		
14.04.2025				X	
21.04.2025					X
28.04.2025	X				
05.05.2025		X			
12.05.2025			X		
19.05.2025				X	
26.05.2025					X
02.06.2025	X				
09.06.2025		X			
16.06.2025			X		
23.06.2025				X	
30.06.2025					X

Annex 5: Template for monthly collecting information/reporting about DCE activities and events for GreenFORCE**TITLE OF EVENT**

Activity ID:

Organisers:

Planned Date and time:

Planned dissemination channel:

Planned dissemination post: (type of communication: i.e. social media post, article on website, video, etc.)

Type of event: *(you can choose between the following examples or alternatively specify: Conference, summer-school, Exhibition, Meeting with Scientific community, collaboration meeting, presentation of the project, expert meeting, etc.,*

Event description:

- Subject/aim of the activity
- Brief description of the content of the event (max. 150 words max.)

Modality: *you can choose between:*

- *online event*
- *'physical/in-person' event*

Additional supportive documentation:

- Agenda
- Presentation/ content material
- Press release (if applicable)
- Link to the online activity. (if happening online)

PLEASE SEND THE COMPLETED TEMPLATE BACK TO Co-PLAN and CEA communication officer

Annex 6: Template for reporting on dissemination activities

Table 6.1. Table for detailed reporting on dissemination events and activities

Dissemination and communication activities linked to the project											Estimated number of participant/Estimated number of reach										Actual number of participants reach (after 1 month)			
ID (PXX_XX_dd.mm.yyyy)	Type of activity	Linked to indicators (Y/N)	Title	Channel/ Location	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Organizer	Impact (National/ International)	Additional comments (if you chose other, please specify the type of activity)	Evidence/Link	Type of post (Original post/Repost) *if you choose REPOST, add the source*	Researchers from the consortium	Researchers beyond Consortium	Students	Policy makers	industries	Media	Civil society organizations	Other	Participants age groups	Gender ratio M/F	Countries covered by the activity			

Annex 7: Event Report Template

TITLE OF EVENT

Activity ID:

Organisers:

Date:

Type of event: *(you can choose between the following examples or alternatively specify: Conference, summer-school, Exhibition, Meeting with Scientific community, collaboration meeting, presentation of the project, expert meeting, etc.,*

Event description:

- Subject
- Brief description of the content of the event
- Profiling of participants
- Link to the event. media coverage *(if applicable)*

Modality: *you can choose between:*

- *online event*
- *'physical/in-person' event*

Photographs from the event: (3-6 photographs)

It is important to have the prior consent of participants to the existence of such photographs and their subsequent use for communication, dissemination and/or reporting purposes.

Additional supportive documentation:

- List of participants
- Agenda
- Presentation/ content material
- Screenshots from the event (if online)
- Number of people reached

Annex 8: Agenda Template

Title of Event

Date, Time - 17.00 (CEST) Modality

Time slots: item title

Person name, institution

Annex 9: List of Participants

Title of Event:

Place:

Date:

Organising partners:

	Name	Organization	Country	E-mail	Signature
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					

Note: The participants provide consent to allow the use of their personal data as provided above, for being contacted and invited in future events of GreenFORCE and for project reporting purposes to the European Commission. Also, the participants provide consent to allow the use of the photos and/or videos from this event to be used for the reporting and promotion purposes of the project.

Shënim: Pjesëmarrësit autorizojnë përdorimin e të dhënave personale si më sipër për qëllime kontakti për organizimin e aktiviteteve të projektit dhe për qëllime raportimi të ecurisë së projektit ndaj Komisionit Europian. Gjithashtu, pjesëmarrësit autorizojnë përdorimin e fotove dhe videove nga ky event, për qëllime raportimi dhe promovimi të projektit.

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